

**ANTIBACTERIAL POTENTIAL OF *AZADIRACHTA INDICA* A.
JUSS. BARK EXTRACTS AGAINST SOME SELECTED GRAM-
POSITIVE AND GRAM-NEGATIVE BACTERIA**

MANOJ KUMAR*

* Department of Botany, B. C. Govt. College for Women, Nangal Chaudhary- 123023, Haryana,

India

*Corresponding author: MANOJ KUMAR

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, antimicrobial resistance has become a serious threat to human health in the worldwide. There are many plants in traditional medicine that are known to have protective and therapeutic properties. The objective of this research is to explore the antibacterial potential of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. stem bark extracts against various bacteria. Antibacterial activity of *A. indica* bark extracts in different solvents (methanol, ethanol and aqueous) was carried out against seven different bacterial strains, including four gram-positive (*Streptococcus* sp., *Micrococcus luteus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and three gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhimurium*) by applying agar well diffusion assay (AWDA) method. The obtained results indicated that the aqueous extract gave the highest yield percentage as compared to methanol as well as ethanol extracts. The patterns of inhibition varied with the solvent as well as the tested bacterial strains. The results obtained showed that *Streptococcus* sp. Gram-positive and Gram-negative *E. coli* were highly sensitive compared to other tested bacterial strains. It has been exhibited that the methanol extract had widest range of inhibitory activity as compared to the ethanol and aqueous extracts. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) as well as minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the extracts were determined for the various tested bacterial strains which ranged between 12.5 to 200 mg/ml. The remarkable antibacterial activity in this study gives some scientific support to the *A. indica* stem bark extracts for further investigation of compounds and in future could be used as drug.

KEY WORDS: Antibacterial potential; *Azadirachta indica*; Solvent extracts; Zone of inhibition.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) threatens the health of populations, especially in developing countries, making it difficult to treat and control many infectious diseases. Although the rise and spread of antimicrobial resistance occur naturally, the problem is exacerbated by the misuse and overuse of antibiotics in humans and animals [1-3]. According to World Health Organization (WHO) report, there are alarming levels of antibiotic resistance in several parts of the world [4]. The high incidence of antimicrobial resistance negatively affects the quality of

treatment, causing complications and severe outcomes [2,5,6]. The result is an increase in hospitalizations and unnecessary costs for health facilities and patients, eventually, resulting in the end of the antibiotic era. People who are not directly exposed to antimicrobials can also be harmed by improper use [2,7,8]. There is the need to expand the available pharmaceutical repertoire is underlined by several recent reports, including the 2019 Antibiotic Resistance Threat Report by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; this document states that in the United States alone, more than 2.8 million antibiotic resistant infections and more than 35,000 related deaths occur each year [9]. These fatal infections are most frequently caused by the 18 different species of bacteria and fungi listed as current urgent, serious, or concerning human health threats [10]. Additionally, on a global scale, infectious diseases cause approximately 20% of all deaths each year and are the leading cause of death of children under 5 years old [11]. Many in the medical field agree that devastating statistics like these are a consequence of entering the “post-antibiotic era,” a time in which the efficacies of antibiotics and other antimicrobials are unreliable [12-14].

Despite the continuous popularity of herbal medicine across the globe, traditional antibiotics have previously overshadowed the exploration of plant-based products as therapeutics. However, due to the growing need for new antimicrobial agents, many scientists have now expanded their searches to include novel plant and other environmental sources [14]. Indeed, mainstream medicine is increasingly receptive to the use of plant-derived drugs, especially those to which antimicrobial resistance is more difficult or unlikely to develop. Notably, 26% of all new approved drugs and 33% of all new small-molecule approved drugs between 1981 and 2014 were botanical drugs, unaltered natural products, or derivatives thereof [15]. This abundance underscores the vast, untapped potential of plants around the world to yield desperately needed novel drugs. In fact, only around 6% of the ~300,000 species of higher plants have been pharmacologically investigated [14,16].

Since primitive times, humans have been searching in nature for resources that permit them to improve living conditions and consequently, prolong their life span [2]. Some of the plants emerging today as potential therapeutic agents were already recognized in the past; however, the reason behind their therapeutic use was not fully understood at that time [17]. The medicinal plant is a term used to describe a type of plant with pharmacological activity to treat diseases.

A. indica is a large evergreen Indian tree of the Meliaceae family, commonly known as "Neem" and serves as a traditional medicinal plant as shown in Figure -1. The height of this tree is about 20m and it can live and provide shade for more than 150 years. It has adaptability to a wide range of climatic, topographic and edaphic factors [18]. *A. indica* thrives well in dry, stony shallow soils and even on soils having hard calcareous or clay pan, at a shallow depth. It requires little water and plenty of sunlight [19,20]. It has maximum useful non-wood products (leaves, bark, flowers, fruits, seeds, gum, oil and neem cake) than any other tree species. This plant possesses a wide spectrum of biological activities which make it well-known in India as a medicinal plant over the years. Each part includes leaves, flowers, seeds, fruits, roots, and stem-bark of the tree has its biological properties and benefits. It is also used in agriculture because of its pesticide activity against more than 400 insect pests and in cosmetics [2].

Seed oil, bark and leaf extracts have been therapeutically used as folk medicine to control leprosy, intestinal helminthiasis, respiratory disorders, and constipation and also as a general health promoter. *A. indica* seed oil finds use to control various skin infections. Bark, leaf, root, flower and fruit together cure blood morbidity, biliary afflictions, itching, skin ulcers, burning sensations and phthisis. Different parts of *A. indica* (leaf, bark and seed) have been shown to exhibit wide pharmacological activities including; antioxidant, antimalarial, antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, antiinflammatory, antihyperglycaemic, antiulcer and antidiabetic properties. The biological activities are attributed to the presence of many bioactive compounds in different parts [19-22].

The bark has long been used in traditional medicine systems for its beneficial properties. It is a multifunctional as well as multiutility natural product and without any side effects. The bark contains 3.43% protein, 0.68% alkaloids and 4.16% minerals. Various studies showed antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, antiseptic, antibacterial and antitumor and interferon inducing activities [23-25].

Figure 1: Photo of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. Plant

Hence, the present study was initiated to evaluate the antibacterial potential of methanol, ethanol and aqueous extracts of *A. indica* stem bark against seven different gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial strains.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of bacterial strains

Bacterial strains, including both gram-positive and gram-negative obtained from Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana and Microbial Type Culture Collection and Gene Bank Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh. The bacterial strains includes *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus luteus* (MTCC106), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC6908), *Streptococcus* sp. (MTCC9724), *Escherichia coli* DH5 α , *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC4673) and *Salmonella typhimurium* (MTCC3224) have been selected for the present study.

Culture of bacterial strains

The bacterial strains were propagated in the nutrient broth medium (5g/l peptone, 3g/l beef extract, 5g/l NaCl, and pH 7.0) incubated for 18hr at a respective growing temperature. Slants were prepared from the separated colonies of bacteria, stored at 4°C temperature and sub-cultured in a nutrient broth medium before testing the antibacterial activity. The chemicals were purchased from Hi-media, Mumbai, India.

Preparation of plant material

The collected stem bark was thoroughly washed under tap water, dried in the shade for one month and then ground into coarse powder with the help of mortar and pestle. Powder was stored in airtight brown bottles at 4°C until needed for future use.

Extraction of plant material (Maceration)

100 gm coarse powder was immersed in 200 ml of different solvents (methanol, ethanol and aqueous) contained in 500ml sterile conical flasks and covered with cotton wool separately. It was placed aside with intermittent shaking for one week. They were first filtered with double layered muslin cloth and then through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the marc was discarded. The filtrate was subjected to evaporation by treating at 40°C in an oven to obtain a dried extract. Dried extract was stored at 4°C until used for further study [26,27].

Yield percentage of solvent extracts

After the drying, yield of each extraction was measured separately and the extraction efficiency was quantified by determining the weight each of the extracts and the yield percentage was calculated as $\text{dry weight/dry material weight} \times 100$ [28,29].

Antibacterial activity by agar well diffusion assay (AWDA) method

The antibacterial activity of crude solvents (methanol, ethanol and aqueous) bark extracts of *A. indica* against gram-positive as well as gram-negative bacterial strains were evaluated by agar well diffusion assay (AWDA) method [28,30]. The diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in millimeters (mm). For this, a well (6 mm diameter) was made with the help of a borer in cooled nutrient agar plate, overlaid with soft agar (5 ml), seeded with a target strain

($\sim 1.0 \times 10^6$ cfu/ml). Aliquots of the test compound (100 μ l) were introduced into the well and the plates were incubated for overnight at 37°C. For each bacterial strain, the dissolving solvent 10% DMSO and streptomycin (50 μ g/ml) were used as negative and positive controls respectively. To test the antibacterial activity of all extracts were dissolved in 10% DMSO solvent to make a final concentration 200 mg/ml.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

The MIC is the concentration giving the least inhibitory activity and below which there is no further inhibition were determined by using the Broth dilution method [31]. Briefly, 1.0ml of the reconstituted extract solution at a concentration of 200 mg/ml was added to another test tube containing 1ml of sterile broth so as to obtain a concentration of 100 mg/ml. 1.0ml of this dilution was transferred to another test tube till the 7th test tube was reached. The 8th test tube did not contain any extract, but a solution of pure solvent and served as negative control. Then 1.0 ml of 18hr grown cultures of each of bacterial strains, adjusted at $\sim 1.0 \times 10^6$ cfu/ml was put into each tube and thoroughly mixed by vortex mixer. The tubes were incubated at 37°C for 18hr and observed the growth in the form of turbidity. The test tube with the lowest dilution with no detectable growth by visual inspection considered the MIC's value.

Determination of minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC)

The MBC values were determined by removing 100 μ l of bacterial suspension from the MIC positive tube as well as one above and one below the same tube, spread on nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 18hr. After incubation, the plates were examined for colony growth and MBC's were recorded [32, 33].

Statistical analysis

The experiments were carried out in three independent sets, each consisting of three replicates. Values shown here represent mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM).

RESULTS

After complete drying, the yield percentage (gms) of *A. indica*. stem bark extracts with the various solvents (methanol, ethanol and aqueous) was determined separately and quantified the

efficiency of extraction. The outcomes of the present study, aqueous extraction gave the highest yield percentage (11.15%) followed by methanol (10.42%) and ethanol (8.74%) are illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Yield percentage of *A. indica* stem bark extracts in different solvents

Solvent	Yield percentage of extracts (gms)		
	Weight of dry powder	Weight of dry extracts	Yield percentage
Methanol	100	10.42	10.42
Ethanol	100	08.74	08.74
Aqueous	100	11.15	11.15

The results obtained showed that the different bacterial strains tested showed specific responses to different solvent extracts (methanol, ethanol and aqueous). However, different solvent extracts displayed inhibitory activity against all the tested bacterial strains consisting of both Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative. as shown in Figure 2.

The maximum zone of inhibition was achieved for the methanol extract against *Streptococcus* sp. (24), *M. luteus* (23), *B. subtilis* (21), *S. aureus* (20), *E. coli* (19), *P. aeruginosa* (18) and *S. typhimurium* (17). The ethanol extract showed against *Streptococcus* sp. (21), *M. luteus* (20), *B. subtilis* (19), *S. aureus* (18), *E. coli* (17), *P. aeruginosa* (16) and *S. typhimurium* (14). Similarly, aqueous extracts exhibited inhibitory zone towards *Streptococcus* sp. (19), *M. luteus* (18), *B. subtilis* (1), *S. aureus* (15), *E. coli* (14), *P. aeruginosa* (12) and *S. typhimurium* (10).

However, streptomycin used as a positive control produced higher inhibitory zone as compared to used different solvent extracts with the zones against *Streptococcus* sp. (25), *M. luteus* (25), *B. subtilis* (23), *S. aureus* (22), *E. coli* (22), *P. aeruginosa* (21) and *S. typhimurium* (20), while DMSO doesn't shows any activity.

Figure 2: Antibacterial potential of *A. indica* stem bark extracts

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for the methanol, ethanol and aqueous bark extracts are shown in Figure 3. In the present study, methanol extract expressed 12.5mg/ml against *Streptococcus sp.*, *M. luteus* and *B. subtilis*, 25mg/ml against *S. aureus*; *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhimurium*. Samples of ethanol extract secured 12.5mg/ml only against *Streptococcus sp.*, and 25mg/ml against *M. luteus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus* and *E. coli*; 50mg/ml against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhimurium*. Similarly, aqueous extract displayed 25mg/ml against *Streptococcus sp.*, *M. luteus* and *B. subtilis*; 50mg/ml against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*; 100mg/ml against only *S. typhimurium*.

Figure 3: MIC (mg/ml) values of *A. indica* stem bark extracts

The results of MIC values of methanol, ethanol and aqueous bark extracts are shown in Figure 4. Methanol extract produced 25 mg/ml against *Streptococcus sp.*, *M. luteus* and *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*; 50mg/ml against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. typhimurium*. Ethanol samples possessed 25mg/ml against only *Streptococcus sp.*; 50mg/ml against *M. luteus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*; 100mg/ml against only *S. typhimurium*. Similarly, aqueous extract produced 50mg/ml against *Streptococcus sp.*, *M. luteus* and *B. subtilis*; 100mg/ml against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium*; 200mg/ml only against *S. typhimurium*.

Figure 4: MBC (mg/ml) values of *A. indica* stem bark extracts

DISCUSSION

Antibiotics are medicines that either kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria. Long-term and indiscriminate use of antibiotics leads to the development of antibiotic resistance in bacteria. Antimicrobial compounds are found in various medicinal plants, and in recent years there has been a resurgence of scientific interest in using medicinal plants for new pharmaco-therapeutics. Thus the need of cost effective and safe phytochemicals with therapeutic potential is urged as alternative sources that can control the microbial infections. Many studies have been undertaken with the aim of determining the different antimicrobial and phytochemical constituents of medicinal plants and using them for the treatment of microbial infections as possible alternatives to the synthetic chemical drugs to which many infectious microorganisms have become resistant [37-39].

The *A. indica* is one of the popular medicinal plants and also found in many countries of the world having tropical and subtropical climates. It is very often used in Ayurveda, Unani and Homoeopathic medicines for its antimicrobial properties. There are more than 140 bioactive compounds found in neem. Azadirachtin, nimbin and nimbidine are the most abundance bioactive compounds found in the Neem. The leaves, flowers, seeds, fruits, roots and bark of neem tree are used for the treatment of infections on skin, teeth and gums. The ethnomedicinal

value of *A. indica* has been reported by many literatures, but there is insufficient scientific proof for further using this plant commercially or in a more effective form. For this, the yield of extraction was calculated because the crude plant extracts are generally a mixture of active and non-active compounds. A number of medicinal plants described in Ayurveda still need to be testified, according to the modern parameters to ensure their activity and efficacy. Drugs used in Ayurveda are mostly prepared by extraction with water. Therefore healers may not be able to extract all the active compound(s) [40-44].

The yield percentage of medicinal plant extracts which contain the bioactive metabolites vary considerably with plant species and the method or solvent used for extraction. Also, factors like age of the plant and the polarity of the solvent used may have affected the yield percentage [45-46]. In the present study, aqueous solvent extract gave the highest yield of extraction followed by methanol and ethanol, and the used various solvent extracts exhibited inhibitory activity against all the tested seven different bacterial strains comprising both gram-positive as well as gram-negative with varying degrees. Among the different solvents used, methanol extract was found to be most effective in comparison to other solvents. Similar findings have been observed in a study, revealed that the ethanol and methanol extracts showed better anti-bacterial activity when compared with other tested extracts [25]. In one more study reported that the methanol extract of *A. indica* produced highest antibacterial activity compared to other extract which exhibited moderate to good antibacterial activity [25, 47]. Abalaka, et al. reported that the organism's *P. aeruginosa* showed the highest susceptibility followed by *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella ozanae* and *E. coli* on treating with the *A. indica* plant solvent extract [48]. However, another study showed that inhibition increased with increasing concentration of the extract and maximum for the *S. aureus* [49].

Although, variable results have been observed in different studies, aqueous extract of *A. indica* did not show any significant activity against the isolates obtained from the oral cavity namely *S. auricularis*, *Micrococcus* species, *Acinetobacter lwoffii* and *Candida albicans* [50]. In one another study, ethanolic extract of *A. indica* leaves showed the best antimicrobial potential against the tested gram-positive bacteria, and produced negative results against *E. coli*, and *S. typhimurium* [2]. Rathod, et al. reported that the aqueous extract proved less effective in antimicrobial activity as compared to ethanol extract [51]. However, ethanol extract were

produced more antimicrobial activity among the different extracts of *A. indica* and also reported the inhibitory activities of extracts may be dependent on both the tested organism as well as the solvent used for the extraction [52]. The differences in the antimicrobial activity produced by the extracts can be due to the variation in the distribution of various phytochemical compounds in the different parts of *A. indica* plant [53].

In the present study, samples of methanol, ethanol and aqueous extracts produced the MIC as well as MBC values a range between 12.5 to 200mg/ml against the tested different bacterial strains. However, in another study, *A. indica* extracts produced the MIC and MBC 5mg/ml and 50mg/ml respectively for *P. aeruginosa*, *Kl. ozanae*, *S. aureus* and *E. coli* [48]). The antibacterial effect of methanol and aqueous extracts of *A. indica* stem bark was determined using MIC, MBC and Kill-time of extracts as indices against clinical bacterial isolates such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp and *S. aureus* [54].

CONCLUSION

The emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance, as well as the evolution of new strains of disease causing agents, are of great concern to the global health community. Effective treatment of a disease entails the development of new pharmaceuticals or some potential source of novel drugs from the medicinal plants. In the present investigation, *A. indica* plant stem bark extracts with various solvents possesses significant inhibitory activity against tested both gram-positive as well as gram-negative bacteria and the results in agreement to a certain degree with the traditional uses of this plant. The methanol and ethanol extracts possessed strong antibacterial activity as compared to the aqueous extract which showed the compounds extracted in the alcoholic solutions were more effective than aqueous extraction. The present study indicated that the *A. indica* bark extracts are effective antibacterial agents that can be used in the folk medicine and will be a good source to treat and control various diseases. Novel antimicrobials from the plant bark extracts could also be of commercial interest to pharmaceutical companies and research institutes in designing and developing new drugs.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The author declared that he has no competing interests.

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